

**Matching supply and demand in crowdshipping:
A theoretical framework**

Ioanna Kourouniotti^{1*},
Email: I.Kourouniotti-1@tudelft.nl

*Ioannis Tsouros*²
*Panos Georgakis*³
*Angelica Salas*³
Michiel de Bok^{1,4}
*Athina Tsirimpa*²
*Ioanna Pagoni*²
*Sebastiaan Thoen*⁴
*Larisa Eggers*⁴
*Amalia Polydoropoulou*²
*Lóránt Tavasszy*¹

¹ *Faculty of Civil Engineering and Geosciences
Delft University of Technology
Jaffalaan 5, 2628 BX Delft, Nederland*

² *University of the Aegean
Department of Shipping Trade and Transport
Korai 2A, 2100 Chios, Greece*

³ *University of Wolverhampton
Wulfruna Street, Wolverhampton, WV1 1LY, UK*

⁴ *Significance
Grote Marktstraat 47 15
2511 BH Den Haag, The Netherlands
corresponding author

Word count: 5111 words + 5 Figures + 1 Table = 5111 + 1250+ 250= 6611 words

Submitted for presentation at the 100th Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board
January 2021 and for publication in Transportation Research Record
Under the TRB's Standing Committee on Urban Freight Transportation (AT025) Call for
Papers

August 1st, 2020

1 **ABSTRACT**

2
3 The emergence of internet and smartphones had played an important role in the increase of
4 on-demand economy. Crowdshipping (CS) is an emerging trend that is expected to reduce the
5 externalities caused by Urban Freight Transport (UFT). However, modelling the CS services,
6 predicting their market share and their effect in the network is not a trivial task. CS matches the
7 demand created by freight transport companies with the available capacity offered by
8 passengers. Currently a gap exists in the literature on models that integrate the decisions related
9 to the supply and the choices that identify the demand and matches them in the real-time. This
10 paper presents a theoretical methodological framework that proposes an innovative collection
11 of preference data in order to develop choice models that identify the need willingness of
12 commuters to crowdship. In parallel it calculates the demand and proposes the development of
13 a real-time matching simulator for the assignment of packets to crowdshippers and then to the
14 network.

15
16 *Key words: crowdshipping, urban freight transport, supply, demand, choice experiment, real-*
17 *time, theoretical framework.*

1 **1. INTRODUCTION**

2 The widespread use of internet and smartphones has turned online ordering and e-commerce to
3 the prevailing method of purchasing goods. The boost in globalization coupled with the increase
4 in online shopping put a strain of the Urban Freight Transport (UFT) system of modern cities.
5 At the same time retailers are asked to make speedy, on-time, secure and sustainable deliveries
6 to consumers. In parallel, local authorities and regulations demand the reduction of potential
7 social and environmental impact of UFT, with regards to emissions, noise and safety. To
8 address the aforementioned issue innovative freight delivery services are developed.
9 Innovative freight delivery services provide “for-hire delivery services for monetary
10 compensation using an online application or platform (such as a website or smartphone app) to
11 connect couriers using their personal vehicles, bicycles, or scooters with freight (e.g. packages,
12 food)” [1] and aim to improve last-mile logistics. Two distinct categories of innovative urban
13 logistics services can be identified. The first one applies eco-friendly flexible light vehicles
14 such as cargo bikes. Cargo bikes are specifically designed for transporting light loads, and thus
15 are especially suitable for courier logistics with a high amount of small short distance shipments
16 in metropolitan centers [2]. Due to their low operational costs, the low driver fatigue that they
17 create and their higher environmental benefits they are currently applied for the movements of
18 food, pharmaceutical and other products, as well as a last-mile solution for parcel delivery in
19 very congested urban centers [3] .

20 The second innovative solution capitalises on supply that can be offered by travellers in the
21 form of crowd-shipping. Crowd-shipping focuses only on the delivery of goods by citizens that
22 travel from a point A to a point B and they can take with them and deliver a package. Users can
23 access the services via a smartphone app, insert the information and pick-up and delivery
24 requirements of their package and then an algorithm matches shipments with transporter. Every
25 citizen with a smartphone and a private vehicle or in some cases, a bike is able to become a
26 transporter. CS companies operate under a variety of business models [1]. Some companies
27 use only motorized vehicles (cars, motorbikes) while others only bikes ([4], [5]). A variety of
28 products can be transported ranging from food ([4], [5], [6]) and groceries ([6], [7]), to library
29 books [8]. CS operates with various ranges from long haul where companies focus on packages
30 that can be transported in a passenger’s luggage [9] to city-range last mile deliveries. Finally,
31 some platforms permit transporters to deviate from their predefined route to deliver a shipment
32 [10]. The majority of companies offering CS services face various issues related to startup
33 operations such as experimental business models, under-capitalization, high failure rates and
34 many mergers [10]. However, larger players have already started entering the market with
35 Amazon introducing AmazonFlex in 2016. AmazonFlex is a CSservice aiming to increase the
36 cost efficiency of last-mile deliveries [11]. DHL has introduced a similar service in Norway
37 [12].

38 As CS has started to emerge as a promising solution to decrease the externalities of UFT efforts
39 have been made to include it in the transport models. One of the biggest challenge is to match
40 the supply and the demand for this service since the first one is created by passenger transport
41 while the latter is generated by freight transport. The prediction of supply and demand is done
42 on a tactical level while the matching is conducted on the operational level. The aim of this
43 paper is to present a conceptual framework that identifies the supply and the demand for CS
44 services, matches them and simulates them on the operational level. To the far of our knowledge
45 there is not yet a model that integrates supply and demand and matches them in real-time.

1 Therefore we propose a theoretical methodological framework that matches supply and
2 demand. To identify the supply we will conduct an SP survey to identify the individual
3 preferences regarding the participation to a CS delivery trip (which is essentially the supply
4 side of the service) can determine the level of service and the total supply capacity. In addition
5 we propose the development of a simulator that predicts the demand for parcel and express
6 transport. Finally, supply and demand are matched real-time.

7 This framework is part of a modelling suite developed under the scope of an EU funded project
8 HARMONY. HARMONY proposes an integrated approach through the development of the
9 HARMONY Model Suite (MS) which integrates new and existing sub-models. This integrated
10 approach is necessary to understand if, how and to what extent new policies, investments and
11 mobility concepts can produce results that are in line with the objectives set by authorities. The
12 HARMONY MS is envisioned as a **multi-scale, software-agnostic, integrated activity-based**
13 model system, which enables end-users such as planners, decision makers, researchers and
14 transport operators/providers to couple/link independent models and analyze a portfolio of
15 regional and urban interventions for both passenger and freight mobility. The HARMONY MS
16 simulates decisions both in the **Strategic Level** (Long-term), the **Tactical Level** (Mid-Term)
17 and the **Operational Level** (Short-term).

18 The remaining of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the literature review.
19 Section 3 describes the estimation of the demand for the service while Section 4 presents the
20 estimation of the supply. In Section 5 the conceptual framework of a platform that matches the
21 supply with the demand is being presented. Finally, Section 6 concludes the report.

22 2. LITTERTURE REVIEW

23 CS is proposed as a promising solution that entails the integration of passenger and freight
24 mobility, aims at delivering goods using the crowd and reduces the externalities of UFT ([12].

25

26 **Figure 2-1 Match Supply and Demand in Crowdshipping**

27 Demand is created by consumers or companies in the case of B2C shipments who need their
28 parcel to be shipped to a final destination. Demand for CS is created on the tactical level and
29 is part of the demand for parcel and express services. CS is regarded by senders as the eco-
30 friendly solution and their choice is influenced by cost criteria. On the other hand, the supply
31 is generated by passenger transport ([13]). Commuters opt to become crowdshippers based on

1 the compensation they are offered and the additional distance and time required to pick-up and
2 deliver the shipment ([12], [14], [15]. The supply and the demand are then matched and loaded
3 to the transport network (Figure 2-1) . At this stage the most important issues have to do with
4 routing and matching strategies. These two issues are interdependent and highly affected by the
5 pricing requirements [16]. Numerous studies have dealt with the demand supply and matching
6 issues, a selection of which is presented below.

7 Studies in the literature have used SP for identifying the most important factors associated with
8 the choice of acting as a crowd-shipper (supply side) ([17], [15] [18]) the willingness to use
9 the crowd-shipping service (demand side) ([19], [12], [20]) , or both ([14],). On the demand
10 side, findings in ([19]) revealed that users are not predominantly motivated by saving money
11 but tend to be driven by environmental concerns. Their findings also suggested that past
12 experiences with innovative logistic services allow users to overcome privacy and trust issues.
13 According to findings in [12], a possible way of stimulating people to use CS is by giving them
14 the option to plan the delivery date and its time schedule, as users in their dataset were more
15 prone to use crowd-shipping services when given these options.

16 On the supply side, studies in the literature reported sociodemographic factors to have a
17 significant influence in the choice of acting as a crowd-shipper. Some of the most influential
18 factors identified were age, gender, ethnicity, income, education, and number of people in the
19 household ([16] [17], [21], [22]). Remuneration and maximum deviation time have been
20 identified as the most important factors for both acting as a crowd-shipper and accepting a trip.
21 In fact, ([21]) discovered that users were willing to travel longer distances, when offered higher
22 compensations. [19]Recent studies in the literature have identified several sociodemographic
23 and economic factors that motivate drivers for working as crowd-shippers [16]. (Le and
24 Ukkusuri, 2019) analysed the Willingness To Work (WTW) as a crowd-shipper by building a
25 logit model that took into consideration variables such as age, employment, salary, people in
26 the household and ethnicity. Their finding suggested that users earning below the average
27 national income are more likely to act as crowd-shippers. This was also the case for users who
28 were more than 30 years old. Other variables that were found significant on this study were:
29 gender, social media usage and mortgage. These results were concurrent with other studies in
30 the literature ([13] [17]). With regards of the selectivity of those WTW as crowd-shippers,
31 several studies have analysed what are the factors for accepting to deliver a package on their
32 daily commute. (Punel, Ermagun and Stathopoulos, 2018 ([20])) developed a two-part supply
33 model defined by both the probability of bidding for a delivery and the bid count on a CS
34 company in the US. Their results showed that an increased in the delivery distance, decreased
35 the chances of receiving a bid. This is not surprising as users are less likely to divert for longer
36 times during their daily commute. An interesting finding by ([21]) suggested that respondents
37 were willing to travel longer distances if offered a higher compensation scheme. Indeed,
38 compensation remains one of the main drivers for acting as CS. Both studies ([21] [20]) found
39 ethnicity, annual income and age as other statistically significant factors that increase the
40 likelihood of travelling longer to deliver a package.

41 In the literature many algorithms exist that match crowdshippers with packages. These models
42 include different business strategies ([23]) and are sensitive to customer related factors such as
43 penalties for late deliveries ([24]). Li et al. matched parcels with taxis and calculated the
44 benefits for the taxi drivers ([25]) Researchers have successfully solved the matching problem
45 by connecting ride offers with ride requests in real-time ([26], [27]).

1 Overall the algorithms that can be found in the litterature focus on offering empty seats to
2 ridders in real time. For the moment none of the existing algorithms include WTP and WTW
3 as a crowdshipper [16]. Overall a comprehensive model that integrates all the decisions that
4 influence the supply and the demand is missing from the litterature.

5 3. SIMULATING THE DEMAND: TACTICAL PARCEL SIMULATOR

6 The parcel demand generator creates the demand for parcel and express services. Based on
7 available statistics the average number of parcels generated by each household is developed
8 The assumption is made that each household generates an average number of parcels daily.
9 Therefore to calculate the total parcel demand the number of households per zone is applied as
10 input. Additional required inputs are the network of the study area and the location of
11 distribution centers.

12 The simulator first creates the number of parcels in each zone based on the number of
13 households. It makes the assumption that parcel and express businesses distribute their parcel
14 to distribution centres based on their proximity. Finally the parcel generator creates a set of
15 parcels with their id, their origin and destination (Figure 3-5).

16

17

Figure 3-1 The parcel demand simulator .

18 The parcel demand simulator makes the assumption that parcels are delivered from business to
19 consumer (B2C). A first version of the simulator is developed that assigns randomly parcels to
20 CS services based on capacity availability and distance. It does not take into account does not
21 take into account the factors that influence the WTP for services and the synthesis of parcels is
22 based on aggregate demand statistics. Next increments will first of all segment demand into the
23 B2C and B2B Markets. Additional data will be collected to help estimate the WTP for CS.

24 4. SIMULATING THE SUPPLY: FREIGHT SERVICE 25 ORCHESTRATOR

26 In a traditional delivery process, logistic operators manage and optimize the supply to meet
27 daily demands. Drivers are expected to be available when needed and their availability is given
28 when scheduling delivery routes. On the other hand, in the CS context drivers are not expected
29 to be available in all scenarios, hence their availability and willingness to deliver a package are
30 important aspects to take into consideration [16]. As presented in the literature review the
31 factors that influence the WTW of crowdshippers are low income, gender, mortgage etc.
32 Deviations from the planned route and the amount of compensation play an important role in
33 the decision to work as a crowdshipper. In addition the majority of the studies addressing the

1 supply of CS services apply behavioural models. Following this rationale, the CS trip generator
 2 employs behavioural models that take into consideration sociodemographic characteristics of
 3 the agent and identify those that are willing to work as crowdshippers. To collect the necessary
 4 data a Stated Preference (SP) experiment is designed where respondents choose if they are
 5 willing or not to work as crowd-shippers. SP data are then applied for the development of a
 6 choice model that is expected to calculate the binary model will be develop based on the
 7 sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents, with WTW as a CS as the dependent
 8 variable. Each agent (passenger) in the simulation environment will carry sociodemographic
 9 characteristics that will serve as inputs for the binary model, and thus those willing to be CS
 10 (supply) will be identified.

11 **3.1 Identifying the supply**

12 To explore and quantify the availability of supply for CS services (i.e. the willingness
 13 of a person to participate in a CS delivery and their elasticity) we employ an innovative SP
 14 experiment. SPs are commonly used in the transportation literature in order to explore behavior
 15 regarding mode choice, vehicle purchase, behavioral shift, product and service purchase,
 16 participation in transport initiatives/schemes or other transport-related choices. The case
 17 presented in this paper is a peculiar case of transport behavior, as the individual preferences
 18 regarding the participation to a CS delivery trip (which is essentially the supply side of the
 19 service) can determine the level of service and the total supply capacity.

20 Due to the lack of available data regarding traveller’s preferences to participate to a CS
 21 initiative or conduct a CS trip, in-depth exploration of such preferences would require us to
 22 employ a stated-preference experiment, as part of an integrated survey to register user
 23 preferences and willingness-to-participate to CS.

24 The SP experiment exploring CS is a part of a larger survey designed and implemented in the
 25 context of HARMONY project (as described in the introduction). Data collection includes
 26 activity diaries and trip chains, other SP experiments (regarding mode choice and future vehicle
 27 purchase), as well as, experiments focusing on dynamic adaptation of travel behavior given
 28 new information or disruptions in daily travel. The CSSP experiment essentially explores the
 29 willingness of a survey respondent to participate in such an initiative given specific
 30 circumstances and varying levels of attributes such as reimbursement, deviation from original
 31 route, content and weight of delivery package and other relevant attributes.

32 The survey respondent will be asked a set of introductory questions before the experiment.
 33 These questions will register the general tendencies and attitudes of the respondent towards the
 34 CS service, their willingness-to-participate to such an initiative independently of specific routes
 35 or reimbursement and experience with such as service. Then, the survey will proceed with the
 36 actual SP experiments. The respondent chooses between participating in a CS delivery for a
 37 specific OD and trip purpose given a set of varying attributes. Table X 3.1 presents an initial
 38 set of attributes and levels that are considered important for a CSSP.

39

40 **Table 4-1. Attributes in stated preference experiments**

Attribute	Levels
Content of Package	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Regular (non-specified) parcel ● Paperwork or mail ● Food ● High value parcel ● Pharmaceutical or other

Weight of package	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <1 kg • 1-5 kg • 5-10 kg • 10-20 kg • More than 20 kg
Deviation from original OD (in time)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 5 minutes • 5-15 minutes • 15-30 minutes • 30-60 minutes • More than an hour
Reimbursement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 € • 2 € • 3 € • 4 € • 5 €
Insurance in case of loss	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Covered by the CScompany • Covered by sender • Split

1

2 Figure 3-1 presents a draft screen of the actual experiment. The trip purpose and travel time are
 3 variables (shown boxes), varying intra and inter-respondent. The number of different options
 4 may also be more than 2, remains to be decided at a later point.

Please imagine that you are ready to begin your daily trip to Work, which usually takes 25 minutes.
 Would you consider participating in a crowdshipping delivery under the following circumstances?

Attributes	Option A	Option B	Option C
Content of Package	Paperwork or mail	High value parcel	I would not consider delivering a package, given options A and B
Weight of package	2 kg	<1 kg	
Deviation from original OD (in time)	5 minutes	15-30 minutes	
Reimbursement	1€	5€	
Insurance in case of loss	Covered by company	Covered by sender	
Choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5

6

Figure 4-1 SP experiment for CS supply

7 3.2 Supply generator

8 This section presents a conceptual integrated urban logistics modelling and simulation
 9 framework that emulates the decision making of logistic operators and the behaviour of
 10 passengers willing to serve as crowd-shippers. The proposed framework will allow the
 11 evaluation of different scenarios where freight supply configurations vary based on city
 12 logistics paradigms. The framework will interact with a realistic traffic simulation environment
 13 based on the representation of the transport network (lanes, speed limits, traffic signals), agents
 14 (passengers, freight) and their daily activities and travel behavior on the operational level. This
 15 framework proposes the dynamic simulation of the transport network by using real time data
 16 calibrated for obtaining a realistic setting of its actual state. Dynamic simulation allows to

1 receive dynamic travel times, vehicle trajectories of passengers and freight, as well as real-time
2 information on congestions and incidents in the network. This information, along with detailed
3 on the available fleet and the results of the aforementioned models are used for the development
4 of the CS trip generator. :

- 5 • **CS trip generator:** A sub-component that has as inputs the freight demand (from
6 depot to customer/micro consolidation centres), the activity schedules of passengers,
7 CS behavioural models, and aims to identify the CS supply.
- 8 • **CS route optimiser:** A sub-component that has as input the travel times of each link
9 and generate routes to implement crowdshipping.
- 10 • **Single-actor micro-freight (parcel, food deliveries, etc) optimiser:** A sub-
11 component that will aim to optimise the operations of a single operator (i.e. E-cargo
12 bikes, delivery bots, electric vans).
- 13 • **Multi-actor micro-freight optimizer:** A sub-component that will aim to optimise the
14 delivery of micro-freight by integrating the operations of multiple service providers.
- 15 • **Freight services orchestrator:** A component that will orchestrate all the above
16 services based on the total freight demand.

17 The framework envisages modelling the adoption of micro-freight and CS services for last mile
18 delivery. This is based in the introduction of dedicated urban distribution centres as pick up
19 points. In the case of micro-freight distribution, delivery tours are derived by solving a
20 travelling salesman problem (TSP) and fed into the simulation environment. For
21 crowdshipping, behavioural models will be used for identifying those agents willing to work
22 (WTW) as crowd-shippers and an optimisation algorithm will match the supply with the
23 demand.

24

25

26

Figure 4-2. Integrated urban logistics modelling and simulation for supply

5. ROUTE OPTIMISER: MATCHING SUPPLY AND DEMAND

The CS route optimiser aims to link the crowdshippers (supply) with the crowd shipping customers (demand). It takes into consideration some of the factors that motivate the passengers to deliver a package in their daily commute: remuneration, package size and travel time tolerance (TTT). In order to match the supply to the demand, an optimisation algorithm will be used to match the CS agents to CS customers with the lowest deviation time from their activity chains. The simulation environment will use Dynamic Traffic Assignment (DTA) to find the fastest route (travel times) between origin and destinations in the simulated network. The algorithm will initialize by querying the simulation network for travel times for the supply (CS agents) and demand (CS customers). With this information, the algorithm will link the CS agents with those trips that minimize their deviation time. Based on results from the SP experiments, a binary logit model will be developed for emulating agents accepting CS trips. This model will be based in variables related to package size, time of day, remuneration and TTT.

After the trips have been accepted, the CS route optimizer creates the tours of the CS trips. Because the simulation environment will use DTA for the route selection, it is not necessary to send the actual routes but the coordinates of each leg of the trip. Crowdshippers new routes are modified in the simulation network for only those agents that accepted the CS trip. The accepted trips chains will be fed to the traffic simulator, where network conditions (e.g. congestion, incidents) and driver behavioural models, (e.g. route choice, driving model) will be used to create a realistic scenario. This will help assess the impact of congestion and possible increases in travel time on the total cost of a CS trip. The relationship between the supply, demand and the different factors consider for matching potential CS with CS customers can be found in Figure 5-1.

Figure 5-1. CSrip generation process

6. CONSLUSIONS

CS is an emerging trend that is expected to reduce the externalities caused by UTF. Currently manifold of startups around the globe have entered the market. However, modelling the CS services, predicting their market share and their effect in the network is not a trivial task. CS matches the demand created by freight transport companies with the available capacity offered by passengers. To achieve an efficient modelling of CS decisions such as WTP from the demand side and WTW from the supply side need to be included. Real-time matching of the senders and receivers is also necessary. Currently a gap exists in the literature on the models that manage to integrate all three aspects, accurate prediction of the supply and demand and real-time matching. To fill this gap we propose a theoretical methodological framework that incorporates the WTW, creates a fleet of available crowdshippers and then real time matches it with the parcel demand.

Given the peculiar nature of crowdshipping, where travelers (who are usually regarded as travel demand in econometric models and simulation) are actually the supply fleet, exploring public preferences to participate to a CS initiative or conduct a single CS trip is an important element of an integrated study and simulation of crowdshipping. One of the innovations of the presented approach has to do with the design of an SP experiment to explore user preferences, willingness-to-participate and time/cost elasticities of CS service participation. Additional exploration of type of parcel, safety and security, deviation from original trip will provide useful information to a researcher or modeler attempting to simulate CS as a distinct transport service in a model and quantify its effects on the transport system.

On the other hand, the demand is still represented in a more simplified way since it does not include the WTP for crowdshipping services. Aggregated household data are applied to calculate the parcel demand. Currently a part of the demand is randomly assigned to crowdshippers since only the OD pair is known for each parcel. Future versions of the simulator will take include additional choice models which will help identify the actual demand for CS services.

The matching in the operational level is done with in tailored way. Based on the WTW and the TTT parcels are assigned to crowdshippers. This matching assignment is the most integral part of the framework and it applies strategies that will balance business objectives (TTT) and social impacts (environmental, congestion in the network).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815269

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815269

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Shaheen, N. Chan, A. Bansal and A. and Cohen, "Shared mobility. Definitions, industry developments, and early understanding.," University of California Berkeley Transportation Sustainability Research Center, Berkley, Californai, USA, 2015.

- [2] J. Gruber and A. and Kihm, "Reject or embrace? Messengers and electric cargo bikes.," *Transportation research procedia*, vol. 12, pp. 900-910, 2016.
- [3] T. f. L. (TfL), "Cycle freight in London: A scoping study. London," Transport for London (TfL), London , 2009.
- [4] DelivCo, "DelivCo," [Online]. Available: <https://www.deliv.co/courier-service/nyc/>. [Accessed 28 July 2020].
- [5] UberEats, "Uber Eats," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ubereats.com/nl-NL/>. [Accessed 24 July 2020].
- [6] Postmates, "Postmates," [Online]. Available: <https://postmates.com>. [Accessed 28 July 2020].
- [7] Roadie, "Roadie," [Online]. Available: www.roadie.com. [Accessed 28 July 2020].
- [8] H. Paloheimo, M. Lettenmeier and H. and Waris, "Transport Reduction by Crowdsourced Deliveries: a Library Case in Finland," *Journal of Cleaner Production* , vol. 132, pp. 240-251, 2016.
- [9] FilmyLuggage, "Filmy Luggage," [Online]. Available: www.filmyluggage.com. [Accessed 28 July 2020].
- [10] A. McKinnon, "Crowdshipping: a Communal Approach to Reducing Traffic Levels.," Working paper, 2016.
- [11] AmazonFlex, "AmazonFlex," [Online]. Available: <https://flex.amazon.com>. [Accessed 28 July 2020].
- [12] G. V., E. Marcucci, M. Nigro, S. Patella and S. and Serafini, "Public Transport-Based Crowdshipping for Sustainable City Logistics: Assessing Economic and Environmental Impacts," *Sustainability* , vol. 11, no. 145, pp. 1-14, 2019.
- [13] E. Marcucci, V. Gatta, M. Le Pira, C. Carocci and E. and Pieralice, "Connected shared mobility for passengers and freight: investigating the potential of crowdshipping in urban areas," in *IEEE*, Naples, Italy, 2017.
- [14] M. Le Pira, E. Marcucci, V. Gatta, M. I. G. Ignacollo and A. and Pluchino, "Towards a decision-support procedure to foster stakeholder involvement and acceptability of urban freight transport policies," *European Transport Response Review* , vol. 9, no. 54, 2017.
- [15] T. V. Le, A. Stathopoulos, T. Van Woensel and S. V. and Ukkusuri, "Supply, demand, operations, and management of crowd-shipping services: A review and empirical evidence.," *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, vol. 103, pp. 83-103, 2019.
- [16] T. V. Le, S. A. T. Van Woensel and S. V. and Ukkusuri, "Supply, demand, operations, and management of crowd-shipping services: A review and empirical evidence.," *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, vol. 103, 2019.

- [17] J. Miller, Y. Nie and A. and Stathopoulos, "Crowdsourced Urban Package Delivery,," *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, vol. 2610, pp. 67-75, 2017.
- [18] S. Serafini, M. Nigro, G. V. and E. and Marcucci, "Sustainable crowdshipping using public transport: A case study evaluation in Rome," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 30, pp. 101-110, 2018.
- [19] A. Punel, A. Ermagun and A. and Stathopoulos, "Studying determinants of crowdshipping use," *Travel Behaviour and Society*, vol. 12, pp. 30-40, 2018.
- [20] A. Punel and A. and Stathopoulos, "Modeling the acceptability of crowdsourced goods deliveries: Role of context and experience effects," *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, vol. 105, p. 18–38, 2017.
- [21] T. V. Le and S. V. and Ukkusuri, "Influencing factors that determine the usage of the crowd-shipping services," *Transportation Research Board 98th Annual Meeting*,, 2019.
- [23] C. Zhang, Z. Du, M. Parmar and Y. and Bai, "Pocket-switch-network based services optimization in crowdsourced delivery systems.,," *Computer Electric Engineering* , vol. 62, pp. 53-63, 2017.
- [24] N. Kafle, B. Zou and J. and Lin, "Design and modeling of a crowdsource-enabled system for urban parcel relay and delivery.,," *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological* , vol. 99, pp. 66-82, 2017.
- [25] B. Li, D. Krushinsky, H. Reijers and T. and Van Woensel, "The share-a-ride problem: people and parcels sharing taxis," *European Journal of Operations Research* , vol. 238, no. 1, p. 31–40, 2014.
- [26] M. Schreieck, H. Safetli, S. Siddiqui, Pf, C. r, W. M. and H. and Krcmar, " A matching algorithm for dynamic ridesharing.,," *Transportation Research Procedia* , vol. 19, 2016.
- [27] M. Safran and D. and Che, "2017," *Appl. Comput. Inform*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 47-56, Real-time recommendation algorithms for crowdsourcing systems..
- [28] L. Tavasszy and G. de Jong, *Modelling Freight Transport*, London: Elsevier, 2014.
- [29] M. Savy and J. Burnham, *Freight Transport and the Modern Economy*, New York: Routledge, 2014.
- [30] J. D. R. Massiani and E. Marcucci, "The heterogeneity in shipper's value of time, results from an SP experiment using mixed logit and latent class," *Pomorstvo: Scientific Journal of Maritime Research*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 69-94, 2007.
- [31] S. Hess and J. Rose, " Some lessons in stated choice survey design," *Association of European Transport and Contributors.* , 2009.

- [32] H. Paloheimo, M. Lettenmeier and H. & Waris, "Transport Reduction by Crowdsourced Deliveries: a Library Case in Finland," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, no. 132, pp. 240-251, 2016.
- [33] DHL, "DHL MyWays," [Online]. Available: (https://www.dhl.com/en/press/releases/releases_2013/logistics/dhl_crowd_sources_deliveries_in_stockholm_with_myways.html#.XXZCti2B2qQ). [Accessed July 28 2020].
- [34] B. Lenz and E. and Riehle, "Bikes for urban freight? Experience in Europe," *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 2379, pp. 39-45, 2013.
- [35] G. Schliwa, A. R. A. S. E. J. and J. and Rhoades, "Sustainable city logistics— Making cargo cycles viable for urban freight transport.," *Research in Transportation Business & Management*, vol. 15, no. .50-57., pp. 50-57, 2015.
- [36] N. Kafle, B. Zou and J. and Lin, "Design and modeling of a crowdsourced-enabled system for urban parcel relay and delivery.," *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological* , vol. 99, p. 62–82, 2017.

I. Kourounioti, I. Tsouros, P. Georgakis , A. Salas , M. de Bok, I. Ioanna, A. Tsirimpa, S. Thoen,
L. Eggers, A. Polydoropoulou, L. Tavasszy

14

I. Kourounioti, I. Tsouros, P. Georgakis , A. Salas , M. de Bok, I. Ioanna, A. Tsirimpa, S. Thoen,
L. Eggers, A. Polydoropoulou, L. Tavasszy
15